

Local Government in Malaysia

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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Structure of Local Government

4.1. The Structure of Local Government in Malaysia: An Introduction

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Malaysian local government along its present lines can be traced back to the British occupation of Penang, which later formed, with Malacca and Singapore, the colony of the Straits Settlements. From 1801 local authorities were established gradually in the colony, and later in the states of Peninsular Malaya, but only as and when it appeared necessary in a particular urban setting. As independence loomed after 1945, experimentation with democracy was undertaken at the level of urban local government. By the time of the Federation of Malaya's independence in 1957 there were, however, no fewer than 289 local authorities, mainly district councils, major city councils being elected.

Two major changes have been made to local government since 1957.⁵⁴

First, in 1965, local government elections were suspended as an emergency measure, and have not since then been reinstated.⁵⁵ At the same time a Royal Commission of Inquiry on Local Authorities was established, which recommended in 1968 (the 'Nahappan Report') the continuance of local elections and a reduction in the number of local authorities. Unfortunately, the proposed reforms were overtaken by an episode of inter-ethnic violence in May 1969. In 1971 the Development Administration Unit (DAU) of the Prime Minister's Department rejected the Nahappan Report's recommendation for reinstating local elections, arguing that elected local government, which facilitated the domination of the haves over the have-nots, and provided for 'over-democratised over-government at the local level', was no longer consonant with the objectives of a developmental state.⁵⁶ Accordingly, there is no enforceable right to local self-government in the Constitution, although it is clear that local government itself is a constitutional topic, and the Constitution provides for a National Local Government Council.

The passing of the Local Government Act 1976 (LGA) was the second major reform, designed to implement the other main recommendation of the Nahappan Report. The LGA, preceded in

⁵⁴ For the reforms of the 1970s, see Malcolm W Norris, *Local Government in Peninsular Malaysia* (Gower 1980).

⁵⁵ Elections were suspended by the Emergency (Suspension of Local Government Elections) Regulations 1965. The Local Government (Temporary Provisions) Act 1973 abolished all elected local authorities and gave the power to appoint local authorities to the state governments; see now Local Government Act 1976, Sec 15; and see Paul Tennant, 'The Decline of Elective Local Government in Malaysia' (1973) 13 *Asian Survey* 347. The issue of reintroducing local government elections is discussed further in report section 6 on people's participation in local decision-making in Malaysia.

⁵⁶ Johan Saravanamuttu, 'Act of Betrayal: The Snuffing out of Local Democracy in Malaysia' (*Aliran Monthly* 2000) <<https://aliran.com/archives/monthly/2000/04h.html>>.

this by the Local Government (Temporary Provisions) Act 1973, regularised local authorities in Malaya, which by 1973 had grown in number from 289 to an unwieldy 373, in five different categories. With implementation of this legislation during 1973–88, and an equivalent exercise in Sabah and Sarawak, the total number of local authorities in the whole of Malaysia was eventually reduced to 138 and the categories to three: municipal councils, city councils, and district councils. As was explained earlier, all three types of local government authority carry out the same functions, and there are no intermediate authorities between the local and state governments. At present there are 156 local authorities, of which 38 are municipal councils, 18 are city councils, which are led by a *Datuk Bandar* (mayor),⁵⁷ and 94 are district councils. There are six special local authorities under federal control as well as three federal territories (Kuala Lumpur, Putrajaya, and Labuan).

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Norris MW, *Local Government in Peninsular Malaysia* (Gower 1980)

Prakash Chacko D, *Reintroduction of Local Government Elections in Malaysia* (Bersih & Adil Network Sdn Bhd. 2021)

⁵⁷ For full information on these, see Malaysian Government Guide, 'Local Authorities, Malaysia' (*Lawyerment*, 2019) <www.lawyerment.com/guide/gov/Local_Authorities>.

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